

Gender Disparities Among Elite Gaelic Games Student-Athletes in Higher Education

Rationale, Aims and Objectives

Male and female inter-county Gaelic games athletes compete within the same amateur framework of high performance. Yet the conditions of their participation are not equal. Female athletes consistently access fewer resources, receive less financial reimbursement, and are afforded lower institutional recognition than male counterparts despite facing equivalent demands. This research explored how gender shapes the dual-career experiences of elite Gaelic games student-athletes (EGSAs) enrolled in full-time higher education in Ireland, examining how structural inequalities in facilities, finance, and institutional support are experienced in daily dual-career life.

Research Findings

Reflexive thematic analysis of four gender-segregated focus groups (N=14; 7 male, 7 female) identified three interconnected themes shaping the dual-career experiences of elite Gaelic games student-athletes. Female athletes reported unequal access to training facilities, resources and financial supports, often self-funding equipment and supplements provided to male counterparts. Women also prioritised education more frequently when academic and sporting demands conflicted, reflecting concerns around long-term financial security. Significant disparities in financial reimbursement were identified, with female participants capped at €290 from the LGFA over six months of travel, while male players in the same county received mileage rates per kilometre. Several participants reported considering leaving inter-county sport due to the personal financial burden involved.

Policy Implications

These findings reveal what this research terms 'gendered amateurism' - an amateur system that demands equivalent commitment from all athletes while distributing resources and recognition unevenly along gender lines. The proposed 2027 merger of the GAA, LGFA, and Camogie Association is the most significant governance opportunity in a generation to address these inequities, but structural integration must be accompanied by cultural change.

Industry Recommendations

The merged governing body should establish transparent, equitable expense reimbursement policies applied consistently across all codes and genders. Minimum facility access standards should be implemented at county board level to ensure women's teams have consistent training environments independent of men's programme availability. Higher education institutions should proactively recognise elite female athletes, particularly camogie and ladies' football players, within dual-career and scholarship frameworks. The Female Player Charter introduced by the GAA in 2023 should also be implemented with clear accountability mechanisms and publicly reported at both county and national level.

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Further Reading:

Whelan, C., Ryan, L., Gomez, J., & Daly, E. (2026) A reflexive thematic analysis exploring gender disparities among elite Gaelic games student-athletes at third-level education in Ireland, *Journal for the Study of Sports and Athletes in Education*, 1–22. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1080/19357397.2026.2668990>

National Smart Specialisation Strategy (S3) Theme: Life Sciences, Medtech & Medical Devices

Sustainable Development Goal (SDG): SDG 5: Gender Equality

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